

Surface Radiation Damage of Mo-TiC *In-Situ* Composites

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ABSTRACT

In nuclear fusion material, Mo-TiC is thought to be probable candidate alloy because it has high temperature strength and is including low Z (low atomic number atoms) material at surface. Argon and helium irradiation were performed with the maximum energy of 400 KeV until 1.5×10^{22} ions/m². In argon irradiation due to differential sputtering between two phases and grooves at interphase interface, blister and flake were not observed. However in helium irradiation, blister and flake were observed. This was eliminated by using sputtered surface by argon bombardment.

INTRODUCTION

In designing for first wall or diverters of fusion reactor, surface radiation damage is realized to be important problems affecting plasma contamination and erosion of wall. From the standpoint of plasma contamination, low Z material coating is thought to be effective, but bonding characteristic is one of the critical problems, and from the standpoint of structural materials at high temperatures, refractory alloy is considered to be necessary. Therefore, in-situ composites of Mo-TiC eutectic alloy is considered to be one of useful materials.⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾

The objective of this investigation is to clarify elemental process of surface radiation damage by means of heavy ion irradiation with Ar⁺ and He⁺.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material used was electron beam melted Mo-TiC eutectic alloy⁽³⁾. The Mo-TiC alloy has a TiC phase of 23.5 mol % with lamellar eutectic structure, of which the average width of Mo phase was 0.4 μ m and that of TiC phase was 0.2 μ m. The specimens for irradiations were cut 1 mm in thickness and were polished with diamond paste. Irradiation of argon and helium was performed at ambient temperatures using a 400 kV Cockroft-Walton type accelerator.

Irradiation parameters were as followings:

Ion Energy	100	400 KeV
Ion Flux	6×10^{17}	9×10^{18} ions/m ² ·sec
Total Dose	2×10^{21}	1.5×10^{22} ions/m ²

The sample temperature during irradiation was less than 50°C by the measurements by both optical pyrometer and thermocouple.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Microstructure of Mo-TiC Eutectic Alloy

The microstructure of Mo-TiC is shown in Fig. 1. The average width of Mo phase was 0.4 μm and that of TiC phase was 0.2 μm as previously stated, however locally large grains over 5 μm in width were also included because of the difficulties of controlling microstructure. In transmission electron-microscopy, Mo-TiC phase boundaries showed good coincidence. TiC phase was almost dislocation free however in Mo phase dislocation of the order of $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$ with dispersed TiC and MoC₂ fine particles.

Fig. 1 Microstructure of Mo-TiC eutectic alloy

Surface Damage with Argon Bombardment

Fig. 2 shows the surface damage in the case of 300 KeV Ar⁺ irradiation. Fig. 2 (a) shows blisters in Mo and TiC phases with large structures above several microns at the dose of 3×10^{21} ions/m². Fig. 2 (b) shows that no blisters nor flakes were observed up to 1.5×10^{22} ions/m² in the very fine eutectic structure below 1μ in lamellar width or fiber radius.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2 Surface damage in the case of 300 KeV Ar⁺ irradiation
(a) blisters in Mo and TiC phases with large structures
(b) no blisters nor flakes in the very fine eutectic structure

In the case of high fluence irradiation above 1×10^{22} ions/m² on very fine structures no blisters were observed, but extensive surface erosion along phase boundaries took place.

In the case of low fluence irradiation as shown in Fig. 3, crack formation was observed.

Fig. 3 Surface damage in Mo-TiC eutectic alloy irradiated with 400 KeV Ar⁺ to 3×10^{21} ions/m²

In the case of argon irradiation with lower energy no such cracks were observed.

But instead of it, pores were observed along phase boundaries. The pores can be observed when the mean projected range is the same or smaller than the thickness of sputtered off region.

Surface Damage with Helium Bombardment

In the case of room temperature irradiation of helium, the blistering in the coarse eutectic structure was observed similarly with the case in argon bombardment, as shown in Fig. 4 (a). But in the case of fine eutectic structure, many blisters extended over phase boundaries as shown in Fig. 4 (b). Since the energy of helium was 100 KeV, the sputtering yield value was two orders of magnitude lower than that in the case of 300 KeV argon. This makes easier to form interbubble fracture parallel to the surface rather than to make interphasial cracking.

The difference in mean projected ranges in Mo and TiC seems so small that it makes crack propagation over phase boundaries easy.

The Difference in Damage Structures Between Argon Irradiation and Helium Irradiation

The most distinguished differences between argon and helium bombardment were the surface sputtering especially grooving between Mo and TiC phases and the blistering area. As for sputtering, as shown in Fig. 5, new surfaces will be made and the energy balances expressed by ΔF could be expressed in the next equation.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta F = & - (d - S_{Mo}) \tan \theta_1 \gamma_{Mo} - (d - S_{TiC}) \tan \theta_2 \gamma_{TiC} \\ & - d \gamma_{Mo-TiC} - \frac{d^2}{2} (\tan \theta_1 \Delta E_{SMo} + \tan \theta_2 \Delta E_{STiC}) \\ & + (d - S_{Mo}) \text{Sec} \theta_1 \gamma_{Mo} + (d - S_{Mo}) \text{Sec} \theta_2 \gamma_{TiC} \end{aligned}$$

where S_{Mo} and S_{TiC} are the sputtered off thickness in Mo and TiC phases and d is the depth of phase boundary groove, θ_1 and θ_2 are contact angles at phase boundary groove, γ_{Mo} , γ_{TiC} and γ_{Mo-TiC} are surface energies of Mo, TiC surfaces and Mo-TiC interphases and ΔE is the stored energy in the bulk and suffix show the phases, Mo and TiC respectively. In this equation if we assume the free energy minimum condition under sputtering condition, next equation will be derived.

$$\frac{d\Delta F}{dd} \leq 0 \text{ for any } \theta_1 \text{ and } \theta_2$$

In the case of argon irradiation the groove between Mo and TiC phase will be more easily made by severe sputtering. And d value becomes more larger. The reason why phase boundary cracks are observed in the case of argon irradiation will come from that the d value is larger and θ_1 and θ_2 are smaller. The reason why blisterings are limited in each phases will also come from deep grooves between surfaces.

Fig. 4 Effect of 600 C postirradiation annealing on surface damage by 100 KeV He⁺ to 5x10²¹ ions/m² in (a) fine structure and in (b) coarse structure (scale mark indicates 5 μm)

Fig. 5 Sputtering and grooving in the case of Ar irradiation

In the case of helium irradiation sputtering are so small and d is comparable with the case in argon irradiation therefore θ_1 and θ_2 are expected to be larger and sharp grooves between two phases are not expected. And blistering can occur through two phases because the ranges for both phases are very close. Therefore the merit of using composites especially fine composites as the materials under charged particles irradiation such as argon ions is to make grooves between two phases and also make steps between two phases. This will limit the extension of cracks in each phases. And if the spacing of each phases becomes very small, the strength and ductility of Mo-TiC composite will increase. Therefore these factors are considered to be effective in suppressing blisterings based on gas pressure model.(3) As Fig. 6 shows the schematic presentations of surface damages in both cases. The merit of composites seems to exist in the case of high energy argon irradiation but not so effective in helium irradiation.

Fig. 6 Schematic presentation of surface damages in Mo-TiC
(a) Ar irradiation (b) He irradiation (c) He irradiation on quasi-honeycomb structure

The Effect of Quasi-Honeycomb Structure

The flaking and blistering behaviors in the case of He^+ bombardment are thought to be specific features of smoothed-surface specimens where the damage peak and gas distribution were nearly the same in the Mo and TiC phases. Therefore the extruding treatment of TiC phase was interpreted as being effective in suppression of blistering and flaking by separation of the blister and flake nucleation sites. Also the quasi-honeycomb structure and extruded TiC phase would be very effective in reducing the surface erosion rate(4) and would be resistant to arcing or plasma instability.

To get such a quasi-honeycomb structure, chemical etching and ion etching were investigated. The former caused preferential phase boundary etching and the surface was polished. Therefore at that stage, the latter method was concluded to be effective in making a quasi-honeycomb structure with extruded TiC phase. Quasi-honeycomb structure is effective in reducing erosion rate(4).

In this investigation, a quasi-honeycomb structure was obtained by irradiating with 100 KeV Ar^+ to 5×10^{21} ions/ m^2 and the surface morphology resembled that in Fig. 2 (b). Fig. 7 shows the result of 100 KeV Ar^+ irradiation of the honeycomb structure. The left and right of the figure were honeycomb structured and smoothed part respectively. 100 KeV He^+ irradiation of this structure was also performed to 5×10^{21} ions/ m^2 and no blistering or flaking were observed.

Fig. 7 Surface damage in quasi-honeycomb structured Mo-TiC eutectic alloy (left of arrow marks) by 100 KeV Ar^+ to 5×10^{21} ions/ m^2 . Region to the right of the marks was a smoothed surface prior to irradiation.

SUMMARIES

Mo-TiC composites were irradiated with 300 KeV argon or 100 KeV helium. In the case of argon irradiation sputtering was two order of magnitude higher in argon irradiation than that in helium irradiation. And the grooves at the phase boundary were observed as cracks or pores along phase boundaries. In the case of argon irradiation, if the spacing of each phases are very small, blistering could not be observed due to high strength properties of composites and also the suppression of void coalescence due to groove along phase boundaries. In this case, there exists an advantage to avoid blister. But in the case of helium irradiation, there were no such grooves at phase boundaries and sputtered off layer thickness was smaller than that in Ar⁺ irradiation, the cracking due to void coaguration was observed through two phases. Composites must be used carefully under irradiation condition.

Quasi-honeycomb structure with extruded TiC phase is effective in reducing the surface erosion rate. The quasi-honeycomb structure was obtained by 100 KeV Ar⁺ bombardment of the smoothed surface, and 100 KeV He⁺ was performed on the specimen. The results clearly showed suppression of blistering and flaking.

REFERENCES

- 1) N. Igata and A. Kohyama, Proc. 4th Topical Meeting on the Technology of Controlled Nuclear Fusion ANS, (1981) in press
- 2) A. Kohyama and N. Igata, J. of Nuclear Materials 103 & 104, (1981) 415-420
- 3) H. Kurishita, H. Yoshinaga and S. Gotoh, J. Japan Inst. Metals' 44, (1980) 395
- 4) K. Sone, M. Saidoh, R. Yamada and H. Ohtsuka, J. Nucl. Mat. 76 & 77, (1978) 240

